

Aminopeptidase B : Regional and subcellular distribution in goat brain tissue

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Abstract : Aminopeptidase B, a metalloprotease has been identified in goat brain. It shows a pH optimum of 7.4 in crude brain extract. The regional and subcellular distribution of this protease was established in goat brain tissue alongwith the distribution of aminopeptidase B in different tissues of goat. The medulla oblongata portion of the brain has maximum percentage of activity followed by cerebellum, cerebrum, pons varolli, thalamus, hypothalamus and pituitary. In terms of activity per gram wet tissue weight, pituitary body was found to have the highest activity. The subcellular localization studies indicate its cytosolic origin in the brain whereas tissue distribution showed maximum activity in intestine followed by brain, heart, skeletal muscle, lungs, spleen, kidney, serum and liver.

Keywords : Aminopeptidase B, goat brain tissue, metalloprotease.

Aminopeptidase B (EC.3.4.11.6; arginyl aminopeptidase) is a chloride activated sulfhydryl dependent metalloenzyme that cleaves specifically the arginine and lysine residues from the N-terminal of the peptides where arginine or lysine is not followed by proline. It can remove arginine and/or lysine residue from the NH₂-terminus of several peptides¹ like Arg⁰-Leu-enkephalin, Arg⁰-Met-enkephalin, Arg⁻¹-Lys⁰-somatostatin-14, Arg⁰-neurokinin and Arg⁰- α -atrial natriuretic factor. This protease besides having aminopeptidase activity shows endopeptidase action on some biologically active peptides such as neurotensin, bradykinin, angiotensin I, substance P, luliberin and somatostatin². The enzyme is involved in pro-peptide and pro-protein processing mechanism in the course of spermatid differentiation³ as well as in the T-cell activation⁴. This enzyme has involvement in various diseases of human skeletal muscle⁵, cancer⁶, hypertension⁷, inflammation⁸ as well as with the diseases of immune system⁴. Its presence has been reported in several tissues like cerebral cortex², testis³, cardiac fibroblast cells⁹, liver¹⁰, small intestine¹¹, retina¹², cattle pituitary secretory vesicle¹³ and human fetus¹⁴ as well as in various cell lines including BE(2)-M17¹⁵, PC-12¹⁶ and K562¹⁷. It has been purified from various mammalian tissues such as human brain², human erythrocytes¹⁸, human skeletal muscle¹⁹, human T-Lymphocytes⁴, human placenta²⁰, porcine liver²¹ and porcine muscle²². The literature reports about the subcellular localization as well as tissue

distribution of this protease are not only scanty, they are conflicting too. While some workers have identified this protease as membrane bound²³, others established it as cytoplasmic in nature²⁴ and still others found that the enzyme resided in Golgi network²⁵. In the light of the above it was thought proper to study this protease and its subcellular localization in brain. In this communication we report the presence, subcellular and regional distribution of aminopeptidase B in goat brain alongwith its distribution in different tissues of goat.

Results and discussion

The aminopeptidase B activity was measured by the method of Hopsu *et al.*¹⁰ with a slight modification. The colorimetric assay method gave pH optima of 7.4 when aminopeptidase B was assayed in the pH range of 5.0–10.5 with arginyl- β -naphthylamide as substrate. After determination of pH optimum, this colorimetric method was used for determination of subcellular and regional distribution of aminopeptidase B in goat brain as well as for tissue distribution in goat. The aminopeptidase B was found to reside in the cytosolic fraction of goat brain as 80.50% of total activity of aminopeptidase B in brain homogenate was present in this fraction. Trace amounts of aminopeptidase B activity was observed in nuclear (5.53%), mitochondrial (4.41%), lysosomal (4.12%) and microsomal (3.03%) fractions (Table 1). However, the activity of aminopeptidase B in nuclear, mitochondrial,

Table 1. Subcellular localization of aminopeptidase B in goat brain

Fraction	Total volume (ml)	Activity (nanomoles/min/ml)	Total activity (nanomoles/min)	Activity (%)
Homogenate	112	8.672 ± 0.58	971.264 ± 45.27	100
Nuclear fraction	8.0	6.784 ± 0.66	54.272 ± 3.71	5.53
Mitochondrial fraction	4.0	10.896 ± 1.18	43.584 ± 2.64	4.44
Lysosomal fraction	4.0	10.12 ± 0.59	40.48 ± 1.47	4.12
Microsomal fraction	2.5	11.888 ± 1.12	29.72 ± 2.83	3.03
Soluble fraction	64	12.528 ± 1.07	789.264 ± 30.66	80.50

The results are mean ± S.D. of three different experiments carried out on three goat brains collected at different time.

lysosomal and microsomal fractions can be due to the presence of intact cells in the nuclear fraction and incomplete washing of the mitochondrial and lysosomal fractions respectively. Its subcellular localization was determined in comparison to cathepsin B²⁶ (EC.3.4.22.1) which is a well known lysosomal cysteine protease. In our laboratory the regional and subcellular localization of different proteolytic enzymes like cathepsin B and L²⁶, DPP II²⁷, DPP III²⁸ and DPP IV²⁹ from goat brain has been established.

Further the localization of this protease in different regions of the brain as well as in different tissues of goat was established. For regional distribution the brain flow freshly sacrificed goat was separated into different parts : cerebrum, cerebellum, pons varolli, thalamus, hypothalamus, medulla oblongata and pituitary body. In terms of the total activity, medulla oblongata portion of the brain had maximum percentage activity followed by cerebellum, cerebrum, pons varolli, thalamus, hypothalamus and pituitary (Fig 1(a)). However in terms of per gram wet tissue weight (density of enzyme) the pituitary was found to have maximum density followed by pons varolli, medulla oblongata, cerebellum, hypothalamus, thalamus and cerebrum (Fig 1(b)). Pituitary body being the master gland of brain tissue, controls and regulates the secretion of hormones to co-ordinate the functions of different parts of the body. The maximum density of aminopeptidase B in pituitary gland may be suggestive of a major role of this protease in protein or peptide processing. For tissue distribution, various tissues obtained from the freshly sacrificed goat were assessed for aminopeptidase B activity. Intestine was found to have maximum activity followed by brain, heart, skeletal muscle, lung, spleen, kidney, serum and liver (Fig 1(c)).

Fig. 1(a). Regional distribution of aminopeptidase B in goat brain.

Fig. 1(b). Regional distribution of aminopeptidase B in goat brain.

Material and methods :

Material : Fresh goat brain tissue obtained from the local slaughter house was used in all the experiments. L-Arg-βNA (Sigma) was used as a substrate, Fast Garnet

Fig. 1(c). Tissue distribution of aminopeptidase B in goat.

GBC (*o*-aminoazotoluene diazonium salt) (Sigma) was used as coupling reagent. Systronics pH meter was used for pH measurement. For recording absorbance Systronics spectrophotometer model 166 was used.

Enzyme homogenate : Goat brain was freshly collected each time from the local slaughter house. It was washed with 0.9% NaCl (saline) solution, blood capillaries were removed and then it was cut into small pieces. A 20% homogenate was prepared in 50 mM Tris-HCl buffer having 250 mM sucrose and 0.1% Triton X-100 using a glass pestle homogenizer. Similarly when enzymatic studies were done in different parts of the brain, these parts were carefully and anatomically removed from the brain. For estimating the relative activities of this protease in different organs, one gram each of these organs was collected fresh from the same animal. The homogenate was stored at 4 °C and used as a source of enzyme for the experiments.

Assay of aminopeptidase B : A simple colorimetric method was used for estimating aminopeptidase B activity in crude brain extract. To 1.5 ml of assay buffer (0.1 M phosphate buffer, pH 7.4), 0.5 ml of enzyme homogenate was added and it was preincubated for 5 min at 37 °C. The reaction was started with the addition of 50 microlitre of substrate stock solution (L-Arg-βNA 3 mg/ml DMSO). After 15 min of incubation, the reaction was stopped by the addition of 0.5 ml of stopping reagent (1 M sodium acetate buffer, pH 4.2) and then 0.5 ml of Fast Garnet GBC (1.0 mg/ml in H₂O) was added. The red colored dye was extracted with *n*-butanol (1.5 ml) and estimated at 520 nm. Both enzyme and substrate blanks were also included where enzyme and substrate were added

after terminating the reaction. The absorbance at 520 nm was then converted into activity units as nanomoles of βNA liberated per minute per ml enzyme homogenate at 37 °C by using the equation.

Activity (nanomoles/min/ml) =

$$\frac{\text{O.D.}_{520} \times 1.5 \times 10^{-3} \times 10^9 \times 2}{\epsilon \times t}$$

ϵ = molar extinction coefficient of βNA (equal to 25000 under the assay condition),

t = reaction time in min,

1.5×10^{-3} = volume of *n*-butanol used in litres,

2 = multiplication factor used as 0.5 ml of enzyme solution was used and

10^9 = for converting moles into nanomoles.

Subcellular fractionation : Fresh goat brain was washed with 0.9% NaCl (saline) to remove all blood capillaries and then it was cut into small pieces. It was homogenized in 50 mM Tris-HCl buffer having 250 mM sucrose in a Remi glass homogenizer operated at a moderate speed. First the homogenate was centrifuged at 200 g for 5 min to remove the cell debris. This homogenate was fractionated into nuclear (800 g), mitochondrial (8000 g), lysosomal (16000 g), microsomal (100000 g) and cytosolic fraction by differential centrifugation method³⁰. Each fraction was then homogenized in the presence of 0.1% Triton X-100 to rupture the subcellular organelles before measuring aminopeptidase B activity.

Regional distribution : For determining the regional distribution of aminopeptidase B the brain tissue was carefully removed from the cranium of a freshly sacrificed goat. The different parts of brain were separated into cerebrum, cerebellum, medulla oblongata, thalamus, hypothalamus, pons varolli and pituitary body. Each part was thoroughly washed with saline water, weighed and homogenized in 50 mM Tris-HCl buffer containing 250 mM sucrose and 0.1% Triton X-100. The aminopeptidase B activity in each homogenate was separately quantiated by the method described above.

Tissue distribution : For determining the tissue distribution, different tissues like brain, heart, kidney, liver, intestine, spleen, lung, skeletal muscle and serum were obtained from a freshly slaughtered goat. All these tissues were washed with 0.9% saline and all the blood capillaries were removed. The tissue was weighed (1 g), chopped into small pieces and a 10% homogenate was

Aminopeptidase B – Catalysed reaction.

prepared in 50 mM Tris-sucrose (250 mM) buffer pH 7.0 by homogenizing thrice for a period of 15 s each in a homogenizer. These samples were centrifuged and assayed for aminopeptidase B activity. Three different experiments were carried out at different time.

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